

Synthesis of Some New Benzothiazolyguanidines and Their Activities

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N-p-Tolyl (or phenyl)-*N'*-(substituted) benzothiazol-2-yl thiocarbamides were reacted with primary alkylamines in presence of yellow lead oxide to afford *N-p*-tolyl (or phenyl)-*N'*-(substituted) benzothiazol-2-yl-*N''*-alkylguanidines. The structures of these guanidines have been established on the basis of the elemental analysis and spectral data. Among the two series of the synthesised compounds the *p*-tolyl analogues (I_a-I_f) have been screened for antibacterial and fungicidal activities and phenyl analogues (II_{a-d}, III_{a-c} and IV_{a-d}) for their CNS activity. It has been observed that the halogen substituent in the heterocyclic benzothiazole ring enhanced the activity of the compound.

IN extending the work done by Bhargava *et al*, on benzothiazolyguanidines as antibacterial agent¹, antifungal agent² and CNS depressant³ we have synthesised some new benzothiazolyguanidines to find out the structure-activity-relationship among the various substituted guanidines. The synthesis of these guanidines involved the condensation of substituted 2-aminobenzothiazoles with *p*-tolyl (or phenyl) isothiocyanate in dry benzene and subsequent desulphurisation⁴ of resulting thiocarbamides with alkylamines in presence of yellow lead oxide to afford the product having the formula (A). The yield of the products were good but dependent on the kinds of alkylhalides and substituent of benzothiazolyl nucleus. The structure of guanidines as (A) with internal hydrogen bonding having a 6-membered chelating ring was on the basis of NMR spectrum of *N-p*-tolyl-*N'*-benzothiazol-2-yl-*N''*- γ -dimethylaminopropyl guanidine(I) in CDCl₃. Along with other normal bands it shows a quartet at δ 3.65 of 2H intensity for $-\text{NH}-\text{CH}_2-$ protons. The two $>\text{NH}$ protons appear at δ 7.55 along with aromatic protons. On deuterium exchange the two $>\text{NH}$ resonances disappear and the quartet at δ 3.65 changes into a triplet ($J=6.0 \text{ Hz}$). Therefore, it is evident that the $-\text{NH}-\text{CH}_2-$ protons are coupled with an exchangeable proton as well as with the adjacent methylene protons. The above facts support the structure (A) but exclude the two possible isomeric structures (B) and (C). The possibility of structure (D) resulting with the prototropic change of $-\text{NH}-$ group is discarded on the presumption that the structure (A) is more stable due to more effective conjugation of the planar 6-membered ring formed by the hydrogen bonding. It is notable that the structure (C) is (B) with an internal hydrogen bonding. According to this feature (a particular six-membered chelating ring) these evidences do not exclude a fifth possibility (E)

namely (A) with dimethylaminopropyl and *p*-tolyl groups interchanged for the structural requirements of guanidines but the structure (A) is much more likely.

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Experimental

All the melting points were recorded on Gallencamp Melting Point apparatus and are uncorrected. Varian A60D spectrometer was used for recording of NMR spectra, Perkin-Elmer 257 for IR and a Coleman Analyser for analyses.

N-p-Tolyl-N'-benzothiazol-2-yl thiocarbamide: A mixture of 2-aminobenzothiazol (7.5 g), *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate (7.5 ml) and dry benzene (50 ml) was refluxed with occasional shaking for about 5 hrs at 80°-90°. The residue was filtered and washed with ether followed by 40% HCl solution. The resulting thiocarbamide was crystallised from ethanol, yield 67%, mp 200°, TLC : $R_f=0.67$ (Benzene-Ether, 4 : 1). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{13}N_3S_2$: N, 14.05 ; S, 21.40. Found : N, 13.88 ; S, 21.63%. IR $\nu_{max}^{nujol} cm^{-1}$ 3165s, 1610w, 1595s, 1575w and 1505m.

Similarly, other required *N-p*-tolyl (or phenyl)-*N'*-(substituted) benzothiazol-2-yl thiocarbamides were prepared.

N-p-Tolyl-N'-benzothiazol-2-yl-N''-γ-dimethylamino-propylguanidine (I) : *N-p*-Tolyl-*N'*-benzothiazol-2-yl thiocarbamide (2.3 g), yellow lead oxide (2.5 g), γ -dimethylaminopropylamine (1.0 ml) and absolute alcohol (50.0 ml) were heated in a glass autoclave on a water-bath for about 6 hrs. After cooling the autoclave was opened and the black residue was filtered. It was further extracted with hot ethanol (20.0 ml). The combined filtrate was concentrated to get the desired guanidine. It was finally crystallised from 80% ethanol into needles, yield 58%, m.p. 147°. TLC : $R_f=0.78$ (Benzene-ether, 3 : 1). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{25}N_5S$: N, 19.07 ; S, 8.72. Found : N, 19.57 ; S, 8.96%. IR $\nu_{max}^{nujol} cm^{-1}$: 3240m, 3120m, 1612s, 1590m, 1570w, 1520s, NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.71 (2H, m), 2.03 (6H, s), 2.35 (2H, m), 2.46 (3H, s), 3.65 (2H, m) and 7.55 for the two >NH and aromatic protons (10H, m).

Following the similar procedure, other *N-p*-tolyl-*N'*-(substituted) benzothiazol-2-yl-*N''*- γ -dimethylaminopropyl guanidines (I_a - I_t) and *N*-phenyl-*N'*-

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF *N*-ARYL-*N'*-(SUBSTITUTED)BENZOTHAZOL-2-YL-*N''*-ALKYL GUANIDINES

Compd. No.	Substituent X	Molecular Formula	Yield (%)	M.P. °C	Nitrogen(%)		Sulphur(%)		Characteristic IR peaks(cm ⁻¹)	R _f * values
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.		
R = CH ₃ , CH ₂ , CH ₂ , N(CH ₃) ₂ ; R' = (<i>p</i>)-CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄										
I _a	4-Methyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	61	144	19.69	18.37	8.35	8.39	—	0.77(R _{f1})
I _b	6-Methyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	73	139	18.35	18.37	8.56	8.39	3200s, 1600s, 1580s, 1520s	0.72(R _{f1})
I _c	4-Chloro	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ SCl	66	135	17.53	17.43	8.01	7.97	—	0.70(R _{f1})
I _d	5-Chloro	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ SCl	49	105	17.92	17.43	7.78	7.97	—	0.63(R _{f1})
I _e	6-Chloro	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ SCl	75	176	17.44	17.43	7.83	7.37	3495s, 3195w, 1635s, 1605s, 1540s	0.61(R _{f1})
I _f	6-Bromo	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ SBr	81	187	15.98	15.69	7.21	7.17	3460s, 1645m, 1610s, 1535s	0.58(R _{f1})
R = -C ₆ H ₇ (<i>m</i>) ; R' = -C ₆ H ₅										
II _a	6-Methyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	73	192	17.15	17.28	9.58	9.87	—	0.67(R _{f2})
II _b	4-Chloro	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ SCl	65	203	15.79	16.25	9.09	9.28	3480s, 3280m, 1650s, 1595s	0.61(R _{f2})
II _c	5-Chloro	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ SCl	47	197	15.87	16.25	9.12	9.28	—	0.54(R _{f2})
II _d	6-Chloro	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ SCl	69	196	16.02	16.25	9.07	9.28	3470s, 3280m, 1640s, 1570s	0.50(R _{f2})
R = -CH(CH ₃) ₂ ; R' = -C ₆ H ₅										
III _a	4-Chloro	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ SCl	48	200	16.07	16.25	9.06	9.28	—	0.54(R _{f2})
III _b	6-Chloro	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ SCl	57	195	16.05	16.25	9.19	9.28	3465s, 3280m, 1650s, 1540s	0.52(R _{f2})
III _c	6-Methoxy	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS	63	212d	16.38	16.47	9.27	9.40	3395s, 3265m, 1640s, 1545s	0.56(R _{f2})
R = -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅ ; R' = -C ₆ H ₅										
IV _a	5-Methyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ S	43	117	14.98	15.05	8.52	8.60	3445s, 1620m, 1585m, 1560m	0.51(R _{f2})
IV _b	6-Methyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ S	59	160	14.86	15.05	8.52	8.60	—	0.83(R _{f2})
IV _c	6-Bromo	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₄ SBr	83	133	12.53	12.82	7.05	7.32	3425s, 1620s, 1585m, 1560m	0.79(R _{f2})
IV _d	4-Methoxy	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS	61	128	14.21	14.43	8.09	8.24	3415s, 1615s, 1585m, 1560m	0.71(R _{f2})

d=decomposition with melting, s=sharp, m=medium, w=weak.

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL AND FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITY OF N-*p*-TOLYL-N'-(SUBSTITUTED) BENZOTHAZOL-2-YL-N''- γ -DIMETHYLAMINOPROPYL GUANIDINES

 MINIMUM CONCENTRATION TESTED : 100 μ g/ml

Compound No.	Substituent \times	Bacterial (Medium : Assay Broth) MIC (in μ g/ml)			Fungi (Medium : Sabouraud's Broth) MIC (in μ g/ml)		
		<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Streptomyces aureus</i>		<i>Curvularia neoformans</i>	<i>Trichoderma mentagrophytes</i>	<i>Monilia canis</i>
I	H	—	—	—	25.0	25.0	25.0
Ia	4-Methyl	12.5	25.0	12.5	25.0	25.0	—
Ib	6-Methyl	25.0	25.0	—	—	—	—
Ic	4-Chloro	12.5	25.0	12.5	25.0	25.0	25.0

MIC=Minimum inhibitory concentration.

TABLE 3—MICROBIOLOGICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF N-PHENYL-N'-(SUBSTITUTED) BENZOTHAZOL-2-YL-N''-ALKYL (OR ARALKYL) GUANIDINES

Compound No.	Alkyl (or Aralkyl) group \times	Substituent \times	Microbiological activity	Pharmacological activity	MED/MIC
IIb	<i>n</i> -Propyl	4-Chloro	None	CNS Depress. Muscle Relax.	160 mg/kg po 160 mg/kg po
IVc	Benzyl	6-Bromo	None	Behave Depress. Muscle Relax. Elect. Shock	300 mg/kg po 300 mg/kg po 160 mg/kg po

MED=Minimum effective dose,

MIC=Minimum inhibitory concentration.

(substituted) benzothiazol-2-yl-N''-(*n*-propyl/isopropyl/benzyl) guanidines (II_{a-d}, III_{a-c}, IV_{a-d}) were prepared. Their yields, melting points, R_f values, analytical and spectral data are recorded in Table 1. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was carried out on developing the TLC plates (adsorbent, silica gel BDH). The solvent systems used were Benzene-Ether (3 : 1) : R_f 1 and Benzene-Ether (5 : 1) : R_f 2.

Screening Test :

For evaluating the antibacterial activity of compounds the bacteria used were *Bacillus subtilis* and *Streptomyces aureus* and the medium used were Assay Broth. In evaluating the fungicides the fungus used were *Curvularia neoformans*, *Trichoderma mentagrophytes*, *Monilia canis*, *Aspergillus niger* and the medium used were Sabouraud's Broth. All the compounds were tested at maximum concentration 100 μ g/ml. The activity results are summarised in Tables 2 and 3. A number of compounds were evaluated for their pharmacological and microbiological activities. But the compounds which appeared to offer the best bioprofile are indicated here including the minimum effective dose (MED) and/or the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for *in vitro* assays.

Compound I, I_a, I_b and I_c :

All the four compounds were tested *in vitro*

against the fungus *Curvularia neoformans*, *Trichoderma mentagrophytes*, *Monilia canis*, and *Aspergillus niger*. Compound (I_c) having halogen substituent has the highest fungistatic properties against all the fungus, i.e., halogenation tends to promote the anti-fungal over antibacterial action. Furthermore, *o*-alkyl analogue (I_a) was found more effective than the *p*-alkyl (I_b) analogue. Although all the three compounds (I_a, I_b and I_c) inhibited antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Streptomyces aureus*, the activity was much more intensified if the halogen occupied its position in heterocyclic ring.

Compound II_b and IV_c :

N-Phenyl-N'-(4-chloro) benzothiazol-2-yl-N''-*n*-propyl guanidine (II_b) and N-phenyl-N'-(6-bromo) benzothiazol-2-yl-N''-benzyl guanidine (IV_c) have been shown to have potent CNS activities such as CNS depressant muscle relaxant and anticonvulsant (*vs* electroshock) when tested on mouse. The replacement of chloro substituent with bromo substituent was interesting because this led to a decrease in CNS depressant and muscle relaxant activity with a concomitant appearance of anticonvulsant property. It was assumed that these activities of guanidines were due to the prototropic change of Δ NH group over the system.

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References

1. P. N. BHARGAVA and P. RAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, 4, 95.
2. P. N. BHARGAVA and S. N. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 33, 36.
3. P. N. BHARGAVA and RADHEY SHYAM, *Current Science (India)*, 1973, 42, 527.
4. P. N. BHARGAVA and K. S. DEVI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 868.